

Special Needs Education

Country Data 2012

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2012

European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education

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More information regarding the systems of special needs education in Agency member countries is available from the National Overviews section of the Agency website: <http://www.european-agency.org/country-information>

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PREAMBLE

The Agency SNE data collection is a biennial exercise with data provided by the Representatives of the Agency. In all cases this data is from official ministerial sources. All data refers to pupils officially identified as having special educational needs (SEN) as defined in the country in question and all the data presented in this document has been collected in line with each country's own legal definition of SEN. These definitions are also provided in the texts.

Data provided by countries covers eight agreed questions – five are statistical:

1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN).
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings).
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools.
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools.
5. Pupils with SEN in inclusive settings.

Segregation refers to education where the pupil with special needs follows education in separate special classes or special schools for the largest part – 80% or more – of the school day. This operational definition has been agreed upon by Agency member countries.

The information submitted for questions 1 to 5 is raw data, i.e. actual numbers of pupils registered in different settings.

The three remaining questions provide contextual information with notes and clarifications, particularly referring to legal definitions of special educational needs:

6. Compulsory age range with a specification of primary and secondary age phases if appropriate.
7. Clarification of public and private sector education.
8. The legal definition of SEN in the country.

Data was collected in late 2012, but sources used are from the academic years 2009/2010, 2010/2011 and 2011/2012.

The following notations are used throughout the document:

* Indicates an associated note.

0 Indicates zero and not missing data.

- Indicates no data is available.

Since the last publication of SNE Country data in 2010, a number of countries have either changed or are in the process of changing their data collection procedures. As a consequence, for some countries there are marked differences between the 2010 and 2012 datasets. Notes are inserted in the country tables indicating relevant data collection system changes.

AUSTRIA

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	706,648		64,114			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	770,762	2010/2011
	307,808	398,840	19,008	45,106		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	28,203		1,039			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	29,242	2010/2011
	10,178	18,025	307	732		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	11,079		536			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	11,615	2010/2011
	3,345	7,734	153	383		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	674		10			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	684	2010/2011
	167	507	0	10		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	16,450		493			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	16,943	2010/2011
	6,666	9,784	154	339		

6. Compulsory age phase	<p>9 years of compulsory education (age 6 to 15). 4 years primary education (age 6 to 10), 5 years secondary education (age 10 to 15).</p>
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>Public schools are either financed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - completely by the federal state (teacher salaries, maintenance of school buildings) in terms of academic secondary schools, higher vocational schools, teacher training colleges, etc.; - or financed by the federal state (teacher salaries) and the communities (school maintenance) in terms of compulsory schools (primary, lower secondary, special or prevocational schools); - or by the federal state (teacher salaries) and a federal province (school maintenance), e.g. vocational schools. <p>Private schools – The majority of private schools are (officially recognised) denominational schools and they are maintained by the respective church. The federal state is obliged to finance teacher salaries.</p> <p>Private associations who are in favour of a special pedagogy ('alternative pedagogy' like 'Waldorf', etc.) and who develop a particular curriculum that is not in line with the national curriculum are totally financed by their stakeholders. In case they fulfil certain given criteria they might also get financial support by the state authorities.</p> <p>If private schools follow the national curriculum they may be given the mandate by the Ministry of Education to provide legal state certification (private schools with 'public law status').</p>
8. Legal definition of SEN	<p>A child is recognised as having special educational needs if – as a result of a physical or psychologically based disability – he/she is not able to achieve the goals of the national curriculum without receiving special provision (§ 8, Compulsory Schooling Act Schulpflichtgesetz).</p> <p>The assessment procedure is carried out by the school district board upon the application of the parents, the head teacher of the school or by the board itself with reference to expert opinions.</p> <p>SEN provision is available for two 'categories' of students.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Category 1: pupils officially labelled as having special educational needs (pupils with physical and/or psychological disabilities) may either attend a special or a mainstream school with additional support (based on parental choice). - Category 2: pupils with special educational needs, but without certification (such as speech impediments, behaviour problems, visual or hearing impairments) are offered 'outpatient' provision by the Special Mobile Service in or outside classrooms. <p>The education of pupils with special educational needs is embedded in the general legislative framework for education such as:</p> <p>The 1962 School Organisation Act (Schulorganisationsgesetz) is the foundation on which the current school organisation (including education of Students with SEN in special schools (Sonderschulen) or mainstream settings) is based. The 'School Education Act' (Schulunterrichtsgesetz) is the legal framework for all issues concerning education within schools (e.g. assessment, enrolment of students, transition procedures within different types of schools, etc.).</p> <p>Special Needs Education in Austria: important milestones are the 15th Amendment to the 'School Organisation Act' of 1993, the 17th Amendment of 1996 and the associated amendments of the 'Compulsory Schooling Act' (Schulpflichtgesetz), the School Education Act and of the 'Basic Act on the Maintenance of Compulsory Schools' (Pflichtschulerhaltungs-Grundsatzgesetz). These amendments have re-oriented the educational system by providing new organisational and integrative forms of special pedagogical assistance for pupils with special educational needs in general compulsory schools (Allgemein bildende Pflichtschulen).</p>

BELGIUM (FLEMISH SPEAKING COMMUNITY)

Question	Data				Total	Academic Year of Reference	Notes and sources used
	Public Sector		Private Sector				
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils <i>(including those with SEN)</i>	269,621		593,713 *		863,334 ***	2010/2011	<p>Source: Statistical yearbook of Flemish education.</p> <p>* Data refers to government dependant private schools only. Data for independent schools are not available. The number of independent private schools is very limited in the Flemish Community. Data on independent private education are not collected by the Education Department.</p> <p>** Home education means that parents educate their children themselves, at home. Parents have to prove to the inspectorate that they can provide quality schooling.</p> <p>Change in data: on 1 September 2009 a new training form was introduced into the Flemish educational system: the associate degree ('HBO5'). The associate degree is allocated at the level of higher education. The courses 'associate degree – nursing' (previously the fourth stage professional secondary education nursing) can be organised by the institutions organising full-time secondary education. The pupils in HBO5 (5,837 pupils) are no longer taken into account in the data on full-time secondary education.</p> <p>*** All pupils enrolled are taken into account (i.e. pupils outside the compulsory school age are within the data).</p>
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	152,395	117,226 Full-time secondary education: 112,452 Part-time secondary education: 3,837 Home education: 937 **	257,813	335,900 Full-time secondary education: 331,866 Part-time secondary education: 4,034			

2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistical yearbook of Flemish education. The numbers given in this table are restricted to pupils in special schools and pupils integrated in mainstream schools. * Data on the private sector is integrated in data on public sector.
	57,261		- *				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	33,034	24,227	-	-	57,261	2010/2011	
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistical yearbook of Flemish education.
	18,418		29,294				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	11,233	7,185	16,992	12,302	47,712	2010/2011	
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	In the Flemish school system there are no special classes in mainstream schools.
	0		0				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	0	0	0	0	0	-	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistical yearbook of Flemish education. * Data on the private sector is integrated in data on public sector
	9,549		- *				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	4,809	4,740	-	-	9,549	2010/2011	
6. Compulsory age phase	The age range covered by compulsory education is from 6 to 18 years old. Primary school: 6 to 12 years (compulsory). Secondary school: 12 to 18 years (compulsory).						
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	Public education refers to community education and subsidised publicly run schools. Private sector refers to subsidised privately run schools. These are general Catholic schools and the government finances them. The number of independent private schools is limited in the Flemish Community. Data on these schools are not collected by the Department for Education and Training.						
8. Legal definition of SEN	Special education is defined as: 'education, based on a pedagogical project that provides adapted schooling, care and therapy for pupils whose personal development cannot be or can insufficiently be guaranteed, temporarily or permanently, in a mainstream school.' 8 types of special education are distinguished. The same categorisation is used for funding integrated education. Reference: Decree, 1997.						

BELGIUM (FRENCH SPEAKING COMMUNITY)

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	674,954		- *			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	674,954	2010/2011
	322,957	351,997	-	-		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	32,857 *		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	32,857	2010/2011
	-	-	-	-		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	32,383 *		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	32,383	2010/2011
	16,560	15,823	-	-		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	-		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	- *	2010/2011
	-	-	-	-		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	474 *		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	474	2010/2011
	225	249	-	-		

6. Compulsory age phase	<p>The compulsory age phase is age 6 to 18.</p> <p>Primary school is from 6 to 12 and secondary school is from 12 to 18. In special schools pupils must stay in the pre-school until the age of 8 and in primary schools until the age of 15 with a special agreement reached by the council of the classes (the educative team of school, PMS centre and parents).</p>
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>The private sector receives no funding from the Community. They are obliged to follow the official programme that leads to the baccalaureate. Private schools make up a very small part of the education system; numbers are unknown.</p>
8. Legal definition of SEN	<p>The Decree of the 3 March 2004 organising special needs education gives the following definition in article 2:</p> <p>§1 Specialised education is reserved for children and adolescents who on basis of a multidisciplinary assessment conducted by defined institutions on the basis of article 12, may access adapted education in relation to their special needs and pedagogical possibilities.</p> <p>These children and adolescents are identified as 'children and adolescents with special needs'.</p> <p>Specialised education is organised into 8 types. Each type is an adapted education associated with the general and particular needs of a group of children, whose needs belong to a same type and have defined as a function of the principal disability common to this group. For children with multi-disabilities, the type of specialised education is defined according to the priority educative needs to be fulfilled in accordance with the age and the possibilities of the child.</p> <p>Type 1 of specialised education is adapted to the special needs of children and adolescents with light mental disabilities.</p> <p>Type 2 of specialised education is adapted to the special needs of children and adolescents with moderate or severe mental disabilities.</p> <p>Type 3 of specialised education is adapted to the special needs of children and adolescents with behaviour and severe personality problems.</p> <p>Type 4 of specialised education is adapted to the special needs of children and adolescents with physical problems.</p> <p>Type 5 of specialised education is adapted to the special needs of children and adolescents with illness or convalescing (classrooms in hospitals).</p> <p>Type 6 of specialised education is adapted to the special needs of children and adolescents with visual impairment.</p> <p>Type 7 of specialised education is adapted to the special needs of children and adolescents with auditory impairment.</p> <p>Type 8 of specialised education is adapted to the special needs of children and adolescents with learning disabilities.</p>

CYPRUS

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	74,455		8,852			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	83,307	2010/2011
	49,889	24,566	3,835	5,017		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	5,796		- *			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	5,796	2010/2011
	3,184	2,612	-	-		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	288		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	288	2010/2011
	288	- *	-	-		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	648		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	648	2010/2011
	398	250	-	-		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	4,860		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	4,860	2010/2011
	2,498	2,362	-	-		
6. Compulsory age phase	The age range is from 4.8 to 15 years old.					

7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	Public Sector: refers to the education provided by the state, free of charge. Private Sector: refers to the education which is provided by non governmental institutions. These institutions are run by individuals, after gaining license to work by the state.
8. Legal definition of SEN	A child with special needs, according to the Law for Education and Training of Children with Special Needs 113(I) 1999, means a child having a serious learning or special learning functioning or adjusting difficulty, caused by physical, mental, psychological or other deficiencies and having need of special education and training. A child has a learning, special learning, functioning or adjusting difficulty if: - he/she has seriously greater difficulties compared to the majority of the children of the same age, or - he/she has a disability which excludes or hinders him/her from using the educational means of the sort schools generally provide for children of the same age.

CZECH REPUBLIC

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	817,965		17,831			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary		
	466,510	351,455	7,817	10,014	835,796	2011/2012
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	69,521		2,902			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary		
	34,129	35,392	1,467	1,435	72,423	2011/2012
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	24,846		1,831			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary		
	11,174	13,672	964	867	26,677	2011/2012
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	6,360		109			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary		
	2,704	3,656	36	73	6,469	2011/2012
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	38,315		962			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary		
	20,251	18,064	467	495	39,277	2011/2012

6. Compulsory age phase	6–14 years, primary 6–10, lower secondary 11–14. 9 years of compulsory school attendance. Children are allowed to start compulsory education later, but all children have to start compulsory education in the school year when they reach the age of 8.
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	Public sector – schools established by ministries, municipalities and regions. Private sector – school established by private bodies, church and/or denomination. All schools are entitled to state contribution. Private schools are authorised to ask for tuition. Schools run by private bodies are funded by 60% of the particular funding formula designed for public schools. Under certain conditions such as a very good external evaluation conducted by the School Inspectorate, the funding of such a school may increase up to 100%. The funding of schools run by church/denomination is based on the same principles as public schools.
8. Legal definition of SEN	A child/pupil/student with SEN is according to the law a child/pupil/student who is or is likely to be unable to benefit from school education made generally available for children/pupils/students of the same age without the provision of additional support. The group of pupils with special needs referred to in Question 2 is defined by the School Act, which specifies the group of children/pupils/students with special needs as: a) Children/pupils/students with impairment – physical, mental, sensory, speech and language impairment, specific learning and/or behavioural difficulties, autism and children with severe multiple needs. b) Children/pupils/students with health risk conditions. c) Socially disadvantaged children/pupils/students. The statistics provided in this table do not cover children/pupils/students described under sections b) and c) as for these groups no separate educational placement exists. To provide data about the mainstream/separate placement, the figures in the table only cover pupils mentioned covered under section a). These pupils have the right to be mainstreamed and/or educated at schools/classes organised for them. References and sources for this information are: - The School Act No. 561/2004; - Regulation on education of children, pupils, students with special needs and of gifted and talented children, pupils and students, No 73/2005.

DENMARK

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	589,520 *		123,521 **			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	713,041	2010/2011
	405,446 ***	184,074 ****	52,213 ***	71,308 ****		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	34,622		1,205			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	35,827	2010/2011
	19,553	15,069	179	1,026		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	12,570 *		686 **			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	13,256	2010/2011
	6,559	6,011	-	686		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	20,719 *		444			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	21,163	2010/2011
	11,988	8,731	120	324		

5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: UNI-C (table EGS), Statistics Denmark. * The data refers to pupils with SEN in mainstream classes who receive over a certain level of support, The overall numbers of pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings is unknown. ** 'Folkeskole' (Local school), 'Kommunale ungdomsskoler' (Local schools for older pupils). *** 'Fri grundskole' (Private schools).
	1,333 **		75 ***				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	1,006	327	59	16	1,408 *	2010/2011	
6. Compulsory age phase	<p>Compulsory education commences on 1 August in the calendar year of a pupil's 7th birthday and terminates on 31 July of the year, in which he or she has received mainstream instruction for 9 years, not including the pre-school class.</p> <p>Primary school age is approximately 6 to 12.</p> <p>Secondary school age is approximately 13 to 16.</p>						
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>The 9 years of compulsory education do not necessarily have to be spent in a municipal Folkeskole. They may instead be spent in a private school. The state allocates grants to private schools – corresponding to approx. 80% of the total expenditure of the schools. The teaching of the private schools must be on a par with that of the Folkeskole. Around 12% of all Danish pupils attend a private school. This percentage does not include the so-called Efterskoler, continuation schools.</p>						
8. Legal definition of SEN	<p>Definition of SEN: People with severe physical and/or intellectual special needs (handicaps).</p> <p>Additional information: The teaching of children, young people and adults is regulated by a number of acts, and, with one exception (the act on special education for adults), the general provisions on special education are contained within the ordinary acts applying to the school area in question.</p> <p>In section 3 of the Act on the Folkeskole, it is laid down that 'Special education and other special educational assistance shall be given to pupils whose development requires special consideration or support', and it is directly mentioned that these provisions may contain deviations from the subject-range of the school, the provisions on proficiency assessment and the weekly timetable. (Additional information from the Danish National Overview 2010: www.european-agency.org/country-information).</p> <p>Reference: Ministry of Education, Denmark.</p>						

ESTONIA

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	106,072		4,782			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	110,854	2011/2012
	70,914	35,158	3,317	1,465		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	6,182		348			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	6,530	2011/2012
	3,335	2,847	180	168		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	3,209		161			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	3,370	2011/2012
	1,685	1,524	64	97		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	1,037		66			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	1,103	2011/2012
	560	476	41	25		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	1,936		121			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	2,057 *	2011/2012
	1,089	847	75	46		

FINLAND

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	531,983		13,205			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	545,188	2010/2011
	345,615	186,368	5,524	7,681		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	45,178		261			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	45,439	2010/2011
	25,884	19,294	94	167		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	5,972		261			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	6,233	2010/2011
	3,449	2,523	94	167		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	14,462		0 *			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	14,462	2010/2011
	9,317	5,145	0	0		

Source: Statistics Finland.
WERA web reports:
<https://www.data.oph.fi/wera/wera>

Source: Statistics Finland.
In Finland learners with special needs are classified into two basic categories:
1. Those with an official decision (45,439). The data presented here refers to pupils with an official decision.
2. Those without an official decision. This second group includes learners with minor learning difficulties (dyslexia, maths, speech difficulties, etc.). There are 125,631 (2009/10) pupils who receive part-time special needs education.

Source: Statistics Finland.

Source: Statistics Finland.
* There are no pupils. In the private sector there are only few small special schools; other schools do not take in pupils with special needs.

5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistics Finland. Primary: 8,376 pupils study whole time in mainstream classes and 4,742 pupils study part of the school day in mainstream classes. Secondary: 5,179 pupils study whole time in mainstream classes and 6,447 pupils study part of the school day in mainstream classes. * There is no data on what proportion of the school day pupils are in this setting. ** There are no pupils. In the private sector there are only few small special schools; other schools do not take in pupils with special needs.
	24,744 *		0 **				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	13,118	11,626	0	0	24,744	2010/2011	
6. Compulsory age phase	7–16 years.						
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	In Finland private schools are financed by the government and their curriculum is based on National Core Curriculum. Almost all pupils are in public sector.						
8. Legal definition of SEN	<p>Basic education is governed by the Basic Education Act (628/1998), the Basic Education Decree (852/1998), the Government Decree on the objectives and time allocation in basic education (1435/2001) and the National Curriculum 2004 given by National Board of Education.</p> <p>Learners have special educational needs when their possibilities for growth, development or learning are decreased due to disability, sickness or decreased functioning. Learners with need of psychological or social support or at risk in these areas have the right to support for learning.</p> <p>Pupils with minor learning or adjustment difficulties have the right to receive part-time special needs education in conjunction with mainstream instruction.</p> <p>If a child cannot cope in mainstream education due to disability, illness, delayed development, emotional disorder or some other similar special need, he or she may be admitted to special needs education. Special education is provided primarily in conjunction with mainstream instruction or in a special class or at some other appropriate location.</p> <p>Act Amending the Basic Education Act (paragraphs concerning support for learning and school attendance) came into force on 1 January 2011. The National Board of Education revised the national core curriculum according to the new provisions so that they can be adopted on 1 January 2011 and on 1 August 2011 at the latest. This data was the last one that was gathered according to the old paragraphs.</p> <p>Source: Statistics Finland.</p>						

FRANCE

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils <i>(including those with SEN)</i>	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	6,105,011		1,320,027			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	7,425,038	2010/2011
	3,555,415	2,549,596	612,500	707,527		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN <i>(in all educational settings)</i>	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	272,716		57,690			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	330,406 *	2010/2011
	117,896	154,820	42,190	15,500		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	16,512		35,482			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	51,994 *	2010/2011
	10,629	5,883	32,141	3,341		

Source: MEN-DEPP (Ministère de l'Education Nationale, Direction de l'Evaluation, de la Prospective et de la Performance).

Source: MEN-DEPP (Ministère de l'Education Nationale, Direction de l'Evaluation, de la Prospective et de la Performance).

* A student with SEN is a student with an official (individual) decision (statement or similar legal document) of special or additional educational needs.
Disabled students have an official decision and get a personal plan (scheme) of schooling.

Source: MEN-DEPP (Ministère de l'Education Nationale, Direction de l'Evaluation, de la Prospective et de la Performance).

* This figure covers disabled children in special schools where the students can also get medical and paramedical care.

4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: MEN-DEPP (Ministère de l'Éducation Nationale, Direction de l'Évaluation, de la Prospective et de la Performance). * This figure covers special classes for disabled students and special classes for students with learning difficulties or non-native speakers.
	186,535		8,317				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	58,913	127,622	2,559	5,758	194,852 *	2010/2011	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: MEN-DEPP (Ministère de l'Éducation Nationale, Direction de l'Évaluation, de la Prospective et de la Performance). * This figure includes pupils who receive support as they are non-native speakers of French.
	69,669		13,891				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	48,354	21,315	7,490	6,401	83,560 *	2010/2011	
6. Compulsory age phase	Compulsory school age range is 6–16 years (6 to 10 and 11 to 16). The legal limits of compulsory schooling, from age 6 to 16, are now largely exceeded in practice. The data refers to pupils aged around 6–15, i.e. primary and lower secondary school.						
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	The settings created by the Ministry of National Education or by non-profit organisations are, for the most part, financed by public funds. Free education and care are provided in all these settings, segregated or inclusive settings, if they are registered by the proper authorities.						
8. Legal definition of SEN	<p>There is no established term in France which refers to the population of children to who benefit from specific measures defined on the basis of special educational needs: the terms used (disabled children, non-adapted children, which covers different types of situations) are all very specific, linked to certain connotations, and marked by a historical situation.</p> <p>If there is no legal definition of SEN, there is a definition of disability given by the law n° 2005-102 of 11 February 2005 for equal rights and opportunities, participation and citizenship of disabled persons: 'according to the definition of the present law, a disability is constituted by any limit on activity or restriction on the participation in social life endured by a person in his or her environment due to a substantial, durable, or permanent alteration of one or several physical, sensorial, mental, cognitive, or psychic functions, to a multiple disability or to a disabling health problem.'</p> <p>The CDA (Commission on Rights and Autonomy), referring to the list of deficiencies, disabilities and disadvantages (order of January 9, 1989) and to the guide table (decree n° 2008-110 of 6 February 2008) will take a decision on the degree of deficiency and on the educational, therapeutic, material, and human assistance that can be provided to the disabled person. As for children and adolescents recognised as ill, decisions concerning admission to and release from medical institutions are based on a medical decision.</p>						

GERMANY

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	8,004,209		704,322			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	8,708,531 *	2010/2011
	2,859,896	Lower Secondary: 4,166,983 Upper secondary: 926,976 Not allocated by level: 50,354	129,782	Lower Secondary: 417,663 Upper secondary: 129,600 Not allocated by level: 27,277		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	-		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	480,024 *	2010/2011
	-	-	-	-		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	306,737		71,185			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	377,922	2010/2011
	96,484	Lower Secondary: 159,159 Upper secondary: 740	16,133	Lower Secondary: 27,243 Upper secondary: 532		
Source: DESTATIS Statistisches Bundesamt. Federal Statistical Office (2010/2011), General school statistics. * All data for questions 1 to 5 includes pupils in upper secondary settings. This is a change to previous data collection exercises.						
Source: DESTATIS Statistisches Bundesamt. * A complete breakdown of separate data for public and private sector is not available. The breakdown by ISCED level is: - Primary: 172,341 - Lower secondary: 227,722 - Upper secondary: 1,916 - Not allocated by level: 78,045						
Source: DESTATIS Statistisches Bundesamt.						

		Not allocated by level: 50,354		Not allocated by level: 27,277			
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	* There is no data available regarding the numbers of pupils in segregated classes in mainstream schools in any sector or age phase.
	-		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	- *	2010/2011	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: DESTATIS Statistisches Bundesamt. All Länder provide for a number of integrated students/students in inclusive settings in their school system. The proportion of integration/ inclusive settings varies between the Länder. * Separate data for public and private sector is not available. The breakdown by ISCED level is: - Primary: 59,724 - Lower secondary: 41,320 - Upper secondary: 644 - Not allocated by level: 414.
	-		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	102,102 *	2010/2011	
6. Compulsory age phase	<p>The duration of full-time compulsory education (compulsory general education) is 9 years (10 years in five of the Länder) and the subsequent period of part-time compulsory education (obligation to attend part-time vocational school) is 3 years. Full-time compulsory education lasts until the age of 16 years, part-time compulsory education lasts until the age of 18 years.</p> <p>Primary age range: 6 to 9; theoretical duration: 4 years.</p> <p>Lower secondary age range: 10 to 15; theoretical duration: 5 years, (6 years in five of the Länder).</p>						
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	Germany has public and private sector education. Both institutions exist side by side and co-operate with each other. As a guarantee under the Basic Law it is possible to establish private schools. This is combined with a guarantee of the private school as an institution. The constitutional law rules out a state monopoly of education.						
8. Legal definition of SEN	<p>The current definition of special educational needs means specific support for disabled pupils. The area of responsibility of special needs education in the Federal Republic of Germany with respect to all organisational aspects refers to the special needs within the context of disability exclusively.</p> <p>Pupils experiencing problems as a result of certain handicaps and/or in need of additional educational support because of problematic situations, as well as students with temporary learning difficulties (e.g. slow learners, reading and writing difficulties) are supported by a</p>						

combination of measures of differentiation within the structure of the general system of support. Remedial or individual educational programmes based on the general structure offer and give support for problem situations during the learning process. The Federal Republic of Germany has a comprehensive framework of special measures targeted to additional advice and support for all kinds of situations that might occur in daily school life.

NB: the legal definition has to be so wide because of the different situations and laws in the Länder.

Source: KMK – Kultusministerkonferenz.

GREECE

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	1,057,619		74,282			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	1,131,901	2010/2011
	744,146	313,473	56,955	17,327		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector *		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	36,011		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	36,011	2011/2012
	27,341	8,670	-	-		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	7,861		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	7,861	2011/2012
	3,951	3,910	-	-		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	26,350 *		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	26,350	2011/2012
	21,866	4,484	-	-		

Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority (ELSTAT) (national official source according to law 3832/2010). Data in the beginning of the school year 2010/11.
<http://www.statistics.gr>

Source: Ministry of Education, Lifelong Learning and Religious Affairs, Directory of Special Education.
* Data on pupils with SEN in the private sector is not available. This applies to questions 2 to 5.

Source: Ministry of Education, Lifelong Learning and Religious Affairs, Directory of Special Education.

Source: Ministry of Education, Lifelong Learning and Religious Affairs, Directory of Special Education.
In principle Greece does not have segregated 'special classes' but some special schools are housed in the same building block with mainstream schools and organise common school life and socialisation activities.
* In mainstream schools, since 2000, Greece has had 'Inclusion Support Units' (Tmimata Entaxis, formerly called special classes). Their objective is to support students in mainstream

							<p>classes with mild special educational needs to overcome their difficulties so they can follow the mainstream curriculum. However, some may continue to function as a separate 'special class', especially in regions without specials schools.</p> <p>In principle, pupils follow a special programme with the help of a teacher, in a group of at least three students (up to 12 students) (law 3699/2008). Pupils' attendance at the inclusion support unit is partially dependant on the learning difficulties of each pupil. Thus, a student can follow for example language lessons or maths for a few hours a day or more (but this must not exceed fifteen teaching hours per week), for few months or even the entire school year.</p>
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	<p>Source: Ministry of Education, Lifelong Learning and Religious Affairs, Directory of Special Education.</p> <p>Accurate figures on all pupils with SEN who are fully included in mainstream classes is not available. The available data is only for those pupils participating in the new 'programme of special educational support by a second teacher for inclusion in the normal class (co-teaching)' (1,634 teachers) or by a teaching assistant (166).</p>
	1,800		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	1,524	276	-	-	1,800	2011/2012	
6. Compulsory age phase	<p>Education in Greece is compulsory for all children between 5 to 16 years old, i.e. pre-primary (Nipiagogeio – 1 year), primary (Dimotiko – 6 years) and lower secondary (Gymnasio – 3 years. However, pupils can attend from 4 years old and in Nipiagogeio they follow a two-year programme (law 3518/2006).</p> <p>Primary education is supervised by the Ministry of Education and covers Nipiagogeio and Elementary schools.</p> <p>Children may begin a form of schooling from the age of 2.5 (pre-school age) in Kindergartens (private/public), which are called Children's Stations or Frefonipiakoi Stathmoi, but they are supervised by local authorities and social services.</p> <p>Pupils who cannot follow a regular curriculum and with severe needs attend segregated special schools called EEEEEK (school workshops for special education and training – secondary education of 5 to 8 school years) and are eligible to follow a programme of compulsory education up to 23 years old.</p>						

7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>All schools in Greece, including private schools, are under the responsibility and supervision of the Ministry of Education, use the same curricula and, after graduation, all pupils take together the entrance examination for Tertiary Education.</p> <p>Special education under the Ministry of Education is organised and supervised only in public schools. Private schools are legally obliged to follow the same regulations as in the public schools for their pupils with SEN.</p> <p>In Greece there are a number of new projects and a system to map all pupils with special educational needs and/or handicap in all schools and services, public or private is being developed.</p>
8. Legal definition of SEN	<p>The Law 3699/2008 'Special Education and education of people with disability or special educational needs' regulates all the issues concerning the education of students with handicap and special education needs either in mainstream schools or in special education schools and programmes.</p> <p>The legal definition of special educational needs is as follows:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Students with disabilities and with special education needs are considered those who for the whole school life or for certain period of their school attendance have considerable difficulties in learning due to sensory, intellectual, cognitive, developmental, mental problems and neuropsychiatric disorders which, according to the multidisciplinary assessment, affect the process of adaptation in school and learning. Among them are included especially those with intellectual disability, visual sensory disability (blind, partially sighted with low vision), hearing, impairment sensory disability (deaf, hard-of-hearing), motion disabilities, chronic illnesses, disorders in speech, specific learning difficulties such as dyslexia, dysgrafia, dysarithmisia, dysanagnwsia, dysorthografia, attention deficit syndrome with or without hyperactivity, pervasive developmental disorders (autism spectrum), mental disorders and multiple disabilities. - Students with low school performance associated with environmental causes such as national language or cultural differences are not included among 'Students with disabilities and with special education needs'. 2. Students with complex cognitive, emotional and social difficulties or illegal behaviour due to abuse, neglect and abandonment or domestic violence are included among students with special educational needs. 3. Special educational needs are also the educational needs of pupils who have one or more mental abilities and talents developed to a degree that exceeds a lot the expected abilities of their chronological age. <p>Article 3, Law 3699/2008 – FEK 199/A/2.10.2008, Ειδική Αγωγή και Εκπαίδευση ατόμων με αναπηρία ή με ειδικές εκπαιδευτικές ανάγκες, http://www.disabled.gr/lib/?p=17947</p>

HUNGARY

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	1,208,087		226,275			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	1,434,362	2009/2010
	712,553	495,534	63,188	163,087		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	66,600		5,839			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	72,439 *	2009/2010
	49,537	17,063	3,046	2,793		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	30,116		1,040			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	31,156 *	2009/2010
	20,409	9,707	401	639		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	-		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	-	2009/2010
	-	-	-	-		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	36,484		4,799			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	41,283	2009/2010
	29,128	7,356	2,645	2,154		

6. Compulsory age phase	<p>6–18 years.</p> <p>Primary: primary general school (6–14 year olds; ISCED 1, 2).</p> <p>Secondary: vocational school, special vocational school, secondary vocational school, secondary general school (14–18 year olds; ISCED 3).</p>
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>Public sector: schools are maintained by local and county governments.</p> <p>Private sector: schools are maintained by church, foundation or private person.</p>
8. Legal definition of SEN	<p>The Public Education Act classifies children and students eligible for special care into two separate groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - (disabled) children and students with special education needs, severe and long-lasting disorder of functioning or behavioural development were recognised as due to organic reasons; - children and students with behavioural and learning difficulties – long-lasting disorder of functioning or behavioural development were recognised but were not due to organic reasons. <p>Reference: Act CXC of 2011 on Public Education that came into force from September 2012.</p>

ICELAND

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	41,780		759			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	42,539	2010/2011
	28,798	12,982	634	125		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	10,129		209			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	10,338	2010/2011
	7,211	2,918	174	35		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	136		0			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	136	2010/2011
	73	63	0	0		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	473 *		3			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	476	2010/2011
	331	142	0	3		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	9,520		206			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	9,726	2010/2011
	6,807	2,713	174	32		

6. Compulsory age phase	6–16 years (6–15 years old = 10 years).
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	Public sector is paid by the government or the municipality, private by others.
8. Legal definition of SEN	<p>Act on the affairs of people with disabilities, No. 59/1992 1 article para 2: ‘Those who are entitled to services according to this Act are the mentally or physically disabled who need special services and support for this reason. This refers to mental retardation, psychiatric illness, physical disability, blindness and/or deafness. ... disabilities can also be the consequence of chronic illness as well as of accidents.’</p> <p>No. 92, 12 June 2008 Art 34: Pupils with special needs:</p> <p>At upper-secondary school level, pupils with disabilities, cf. Article 2 of Act No. 59 from 1992 on Affairs of People with Disabilities, and pupils with emotional or social difficulties shall be provided with instruction and special study support. Specialised assistance and appropriate facilities shall be provided as considered necessary by the Ministry of Education, Science and Culture. Pupils with special needs shall study side by side with other pupils whenever possible.</p> <p>The Minister of Education, Science and Culture may, with agreement with an upper-secondary school, authorise operation of special study programmes for pupils with disabilities in upper-secondary schools.</p> <p>Pupils with reading difficulties shall, whenever possible, have access to specialised instructional material. The upper-secondary school defines in its school curriculum guide how it conducts screening and analysis for dyslexia, as well as its measures for follow-up and support for pupils analysed as dyslexic.</p> <p>Upper-secondary schools shall strive to provide special support to pupils that have specific study difficulties or illnesses.</p>

IRELAND

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	668,245		- *			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary		
	419,393	248,852	-	-	668,245	2010/2011
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	39,116		- *			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary		
	25,017	14,099	-	-	39,116	2010/2011
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	5,410		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary		
	5,410	- *	-	-	5,410	2010/2011
	<p>Source: Department of Education and Skills.</p> <p>* The total figure provided applies to public sector schools only as private schools are not obliged to return data to the Department of Education and Skills.</p>					
	<p>Source: Department of Education and Skills.</p> <p>* No breakdown is available for the private sector. This applies to questions 2–5.</p> <p>The figures provided here are totals for questions 3, 4 and 5. Please refer to explanatory notes provided for these questions.</p> <p>The figure for primary schools does not include children with high incidence SEN who are resourced under the General Allocation Model. These children receive additional support in schools without requiring formal diagnosis. Reliable figures for the number of children receiving additional support without a formal diagnosis are not available.</p>					
	<p>Source: Department of Education and Skills.</p> <p>This figure refers to pupils of compulsory school age (6–16 years) in special schools.</p> <p>* Special schools in Ireland are designated primary schools, but some special schools also provide education to children of secondary school age. Of the 5,410 pupils aged 6–16 years in special schools, 2,471 of these pupils are of secondary school age (13–16 years).</p> <p>In addition to the pupils of compulsory school age, 1,133 pupils outside of compulsory school age were enrolled in special schools, i.e. pupils who are under the age of 6 years, or aged 17 years or over.</p> <p>The figures provided here for special schools refer only</p>					

							to special schools for pupils with assessed special educational needs. In the returns for years prior to 2008/2009, the figures for special schools included schools for children with special educational needs, as well as other schools which cater for children who are not included in mainstream school environments, such as hospital schools, schools for members of the Traveller community and schools for young offenders. The latter categories are not included in the data from 2008/2009 onwards.
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Department of Education and Skills. * There is a total of 2,774 pupils in special classes in mainstream primary schools. 2,302 is an estimate of those pupils aged 6–16, i.e. those who are in compulsory education. The figures provided here refer to primary schools only. Figures for pupils in special classes in mainstream secondary schools are not available for 2010/2011.
	2,302		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	2,302 *	2010/2011	
	2,302	-	-	-			
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Department of Education and Skills. * The figure of 17,305 for primary refers to children with low incidence SEN, on whose behalf the NCSE has allocated resource teacher hours. This figure may not include a minority of children in the age range 6–12 years on whose behalf resource teacher hours were allocated before the NCSE assumed the resource allocation function in 2005. ** The figure for Secondary includes children in receipt of resources through the NCSE for both low and high incidence SEN.
	31,404		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	31,404	2010/2011	
	17,305 *	14,099 **	-	-			
6. Compulsory age phase	Education in Ireland is compulsory from age 6 to 16 or until students have completed three years of second level education.						
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	Public schools (including some fee-paying schools) are grant-aided by the state. Private schools do not receive funding from the state.						
8. Legal definition of SEN	'Special educational needs means, in relation to a person, a restriction in the capacity of the person to participate in and benefit from education on account of an enduring physical, sensory, mental health or learning disability, or any other condition which results in a person learning differently from a person without that condition' (Education for Persons with Special Educational Needs Act 2004).						

ITALY

Question	Data				Total	Academic Year of Reference	Notes and sources used
	Public Sector		Private Sector				
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	6,721,798		556,220		7,278,018	2010/2011	<p>Source: General Directorate for Informatics and Statistics – Ministry of Education, University and Research.</p> <p>Available from: http://www.istruzione.it/web/istruzione/disabilita</p> <p>* The data here covers Primary schools only. This applies to all questions.</p> <p>In addition there are 1,001,818 pupils in pre-primary education in the public sector and 686,022 in the private sector.</p> <p>** Secondary data includes post-primary education (called 'lower secondary education') and pre-diploma education and training (called 'upper secondary education').</p> <p>Students in Universities and Academies are excluded.</p>
	Primary *	Secondary **	Primary *	Secondary **			
	2,573,147 *	1,678,059 2,470,592 Total 4,148,651	254,417	109,444 192,359 Total 301,803			
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	179,009		10,554		189,563	2010/2011	<p>Source: General Directorate for Informatics and Statistics – Ministry of Education, University and Research</p> <p>Available on: http://www.istruzione.it/web/istruzione/disabilita</p> <p>* In addition there are 14,409 pupils in mainstream pre-primary education in the public sector and 6,384 in the private sector.</p>
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	74,034	104,975	5,165	5,389			
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	1,835		-		1,835 *	2010/2011	<p>Source: General Directorate for Informatics and Statistics – Ministry of Education, University and Research</p> <p>Additional information: MIUR, L'handicap e la scuola, i dati dell'integrazione – 1999/2000; OECD Special Education Needs, Statistics and Indicators, 2000; ISTAT – Disabilità in cifre.</p> <p>* In Italy there are 71 special schools (out of</p>
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	1,278	557	-	-			

							<p>the mainstream education).</p> <p>Data from MIUR, OECD, ISTAT all indicate that there are around 1.6 special schools per 100,000 students of compulsory school age.</p> <p>Of the 71 special schools/care centres only 0.30% are private, so the available approximate data of the number of pupils attending private segregated/special settings has been included within public sector data.</p> <p>Due to the small number of institutes/separate special schools/ segregated educational centres throughout the country, the data provided is approximate without any distinction between primary and secondary public and private sectors. The approximate data includes the number of pupils attending state and private schools, rehabilitation centres and institutes of care separated from the mainstream and regular courses of education.</p> <p>The total figure includes pupils receiving short and long term periods of rehabilitation. According to the law in force, any form of rehabilitation, therapy, hospitalisation and care that could include aspects of teaching and learning are seen as a transient state for the pupil with SEN or a parallel activity of education, offered in rare cases in order to better support access and the right to education within the pupil's local mainstream school.</p>
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	* The Italian Law in force does not foresee any possibility to create a special/ segregated/separated class within a mainstream school. Pupils have to be included in regular classes without any discrimination, differentiation or any form of segregation.
	0		0				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	0	0	0	0	0 *	2010/2011	

5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: General Directorate for Informatics and Statistics – Ministry of Education, University and Research.
	177,174		10,554				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	72,756	57,795 46,623 Total: 104,418	5,165	3,363 2,026 Total: 5,389			
6. Compulsory age phase	From 6 to 16 years old.						
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>Public schools are funded by the State. The internal school staff (teachers, headmasters and administrative assistants) are selected by national public examination and paid for by the State.</p> <p>Private schools are funded only by private sectors as parents, associations, charities, etc. The school staff is selected and paid by the school management. To have an 'official recognition', any private school/institute has to accept the enrolment of pupils with SEN.</p> <p>All kinds of schools have to follow the national guidelines on education and they are periodically visited by Ministerial Supervisors.</p>						
8. Legal definition of SEN	<p>The Law No. 104, dated 5/2/1992 sets out who is a person with disabilities: a 'person with disabilities' is anyone who presents a physical, psychological, sensory impairment, permanent or progressive, that causes a learning, social, working difficulty and that causes a situation of disadvantage or social marginalisation.</p> <p>The Presidential Decree dated on 19.5.2006 established that the Medical Commission in charge for delivery the certificate of disability has to refer to the International Indicators OMS – ICF.</p>						

LATVIA

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	167,760		- *			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	167,760	2011/2012
	113,410	54,350	-	-		
<p>Source: All data for questions 1–5 is taken from the statistics report of the Ministry of Education and Science.</p> <p>* Data about the number of pupils in the private sector is included in the public sector data. No separate data is available. This applies to questions 1 to 5.</p> <p>There is also no data about those students of compulsory school age who receive their education in part-time schools or so-called ‘evening schools’.</p> <p>The data is available on the web site: www.izm.gov.lv</p>						
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	9,726		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	9,726	2011/2012
	6,204	3,522	-	-		
<p>Source: Statistical data of the Ministry of Education and Science.</p>						
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	6,172		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	6,172	2011/2012
	3,589	2,583	-	-		
<p>Source: Statistical data of the Ministry of Education and Science.</p>						
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	1,072		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	1,072	2011/2012
	834	238	-	-		
<p>Source: Statistical data of the Ministry of Education and Science.</p>						

5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Statistical data of the Ministry of Education and Science.
	2,482		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	1,781	701	-	-			
6. Compulsory age phase	Basic education is compulsory (Education Law, Section 4) in Latvia and it is from the age of 7 till 16 (9 years: grades 1 to 9), but it is possible to continue to acquire basic education until reaching the age of 18. Grades 1 to 6 (ages 7 to 13) could be called primary education and grades 7 to 9 (ages 14 to 16) – lower secondary education, but in legislation these levels are not officially recognised.						
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>According to Education Law (1999) Section 23: Procedures for the Foundation, Reorganisation and Dissolution of Educational Institutions:</p> <p>(1) State educational institutions shall be founded, reorganised and dissolved by the Cabinet pursuant to proposal by the Minister for Education and Science or the Minister for another sector.</p> <p>(2) Local government educational institutions shall be founded, reorganised and dissolved by local governments, co-ordinating with the Ministry of Education and Science or the relevant sector ministry and the Ministry of Education and Science.</p> <p>(3) Private educational institutions shall be founded, reorganised and dissolved by legal persons and natural persons. The state and local governments may participate in the foundation of the private undertakings (companies).</p> <p>(4) A foreign legal person may found, reorganise and dissolve an educational institution in accordance with this Law and other laws, as well as with international agreements.</p>						
8. Legal definition of SEN	<p>Education Law, Section 1, paragraph 24 states that Special education is general and professional education adapted for persons with special needs and health problems, or with special needs or health problems.</p> <p>The amendments to the Law on General Education adopted in 2011 state that: 'Special needs are the need for appropriate support and rehabilitation that give learners the opportunity to acquire educational programs according to their health condition, abilities and level of development. Availability of adequate support measures for learners with special needs who are included into a general education institution shall be ensured by the educational institution. Individual education plans should be developed for every learner with special needs who is included in general education classroom.'</p>						

LITHUANIA

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	387,227		5,695			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	392,922	2011/2012
	110,114	277,113	1,325	4,370		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	46,378		230			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	46,608	2011/2012
	23,524	22,854	89	141		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	3,826		38			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	3,864	2011/2012
	1,039	2,787	15	23		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	814		6			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	820	2011/2012
	290	524	1	5		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	41,738		186			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	41,924	2011/2012
	22,195	19,543	73	113		

6. Compulsory age phase	<p>The compulsory education in Lithuania is from 6/7 to 18 years. For pupils with severe profound dysfunctions, it can be from 6/7 to 21 years of age.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Primary education is from 6/7 to 10/11 years of age. - General lower secondary education is from 10/11 to 16/17 years of age. - General lower secondary education (Gymnasium grade) is from 14/15 to 16/17 years of age. - General lower secondary education (Youth school) is from 11/12 to 18 years of age.
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>Law amending the law on Education of the Republic of Lithuania (2011).</p> <p>Article 28.paragraphs 4. The Minister of Education and Science, together with municipalities and the government, shall ensure the sufficient network of state and municipal vocational training schools and general education schools designated for country's (region's) learners with special educational needs; 6. The municipality must have an optimal network of providers of primary, basic, secondary and non-formal education programmes designated for children and adults, ensuring individuals' learning and securing their right to receive instruction in the state language, as well as a network of institutions that provide assistance to learners, teachers and schools. In areas where the municipality does not ensure the individuals' right to receive instruction in the state language according preschool, pre-primary and general education curricula, state schools may be established in which curricula are carried out in the state language; 9. The State and municipalities shall create conditions for establishment and operation of non-state schools;10. The network of providers of non-formal education shall be established by the State, municipalities, natural and legal persons, legal persons or other organisations established in a member state or any other foreign state, or their branches.</p>
8. Legal definition of SEN	<p>Law amending the law on Education of the Republic of Lithuania (2011).</p> <p>SEN – a need for assistance and services in education process that occurs due to being exceptionally gifted, having congenital or acquired disorders or disadvantages in person's surrounding.</p>

LUXEMBOURG

Question	Data				Notes and sources used		
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Ministry of Education. Luxembourg: www.men.lu * No data is available for school year 2009/2010.
	66,318		4,372				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	Pre-primary: 14,156 Primary: 32,096 Total: 46,252	20,066	4,372	- *	70,690	2009/2010	
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Ministry of Education, Luxembourg. * No breakdown data is available for school year 2009/2010. This figure is the total for pupils in public sector primary and secondary schools.
	-		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	1,095 *	2009/2010	
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Ministry of Education, Luxembourg. * No breakdown data is available for school year 2009/2010. This figure is the total for pupils in public sector primary and secondary special schools.
	-		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	608 *	2009/2010	
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	* Separate data is not available as these pupils are considered to be on the roll of special schools.
	-		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	- *	-	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Ministry of Education, Luxembourg. * No breakdown data is available for school year 2009/2010. This figure is the total for pupils with SEN in public sector primary and secondary schools.
	-		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	487 *	2009/2010	

6. Compulsory age phase	Compulsory education in Luxembourg covers 11 years: two years of pre-primary school (4 to 6 years), 6 years of primary school (6 to 12 years), and the first three years of secondary school (12 to 15 years). 1 year of non-compulsory school is offered to children aged 3 to 4 years.
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	The Luxembourg State is in charge of organising and controlling the educational system. Public and private schools teach the same topics. In Luxembourg most primary and secondary schools are public schools. Public education is free of charge. Private schools are nearly all Catholic schools and are not free of charge. Private schools in these figures are grant-aided schools. Non grant-aided international schools are not listed in these statistics.
8. Legal definition of SEN	Law of Special Education of 1973: 'The Government makes sure that every child because of his/her mental, sensory, emotional or motor particularities gets the instruction required by his state or situation in the structures of Special Education.' Law of 1993 states that the named children can be included in mainstream schools.

MALTA

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	26,974		19,973			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	46,947	2011/2012
	13,517	13,457	10,109	9,864		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	1,710		862			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	2,572	2011/2012
	978	732	435	427		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	54		0			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	54	2011/2012
	14	40	0	0		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	11		0			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	11 *	2011/2012
	0	11	0	0		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	1,645		862			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	2,507	2011/2012
	964	681	435	427		

6. Compulsory age phase	For mainstream settings compulsory school age is from 5 to 16 years.
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	Public sector education is where students attend educational provision provided by the State. Public sector education is free. Private sector education (also called non-state education) includes Church Schools and Independent Schools. Parents of children attending Church Schools do not pay tuition fees. These are subsidised by the State as per agreement between the Government of Malta and the Church. On the other hand, parents who send their children to Independent Schools pay fees. There are no segregated special schools in the private education sector.
8. Legal definition of SEN	'A minor shall be deemed to have special educational needs when that minor has special difficulties of physical, sensory, intellectual or psychological nature.' Article 45 (2), Education Act, 2006, Chapter 327 of the Laws of Malta.

NETHERLANDS

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	2,422,852		- *			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	2,422,852	2011/2012
	1,446,161	976,691	-	-		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	106,698		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	106,698	2011/2012
	53,898	52,800	-	-		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	66,085		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	66,085	2011/2012
	32,797	33,288	-	-		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	-		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	- *	-
	-	-	-	-		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	40,613		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	40,613	2009/2010
	21,101	19,512	-	-		

6. Compulsory age phase	<p>Compulsory schooling is from 5 to 18 years. This is a change since previous data collection exercises – the compulsory schooling period has been extended.</p> <p>Primary schooling is from 4 to 12 years of age.</p> <p>Secondary schooling is from 12 to 18 years of age.</p>
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>Private schools do not receive any funding from the Government.</p> <p>No data is available on pupils in private education.</p>
8. Legal definition of SEN	<p>The law on the Expertise Centres (WEC 2003) states that pupils are eligible for special education if they meet certain criteria. These are largely based on existing practice.</p> <p>Criteria for the visually impaired are a visual acuity: <0.3 or a visual field: < 30 and limited participation in education as a result of the visual impairment.</p> <p>For hearing impaired pupils a hearing loss > 80 dB (or for hard of hearing pupils 35–80 dB) and limited participation in education are required.</p> <p>The decision to provide extra funding for mentally disabled pupils will be based largely on IQ < 60, for physically impaired and chronically ill pupils medical data showing diagnosed disabilities/illness are needed.</p> <p>The criteria for behaviourally disturbed pupils require a diagnosis in terms of categories of the DSM-IV, problems at school, at home and in the community and a limited participation in education as a result of the behaviour problems.</p>

NORWAY

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	599,663		16,310			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	615,973	2010/2011
	413,328	186,335	10,005	6,305		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	50,563		1,616			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	52,179	2010/2011
	29,959	20,604	795	821		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	1,821		60			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	1,881	2010/2011
	792	1,029	22	38		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	3,103 **		98			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	3,201 *	2010/2011
	-	-	-	-		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	45,639		1,458			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	47,097 *	2010/2011
	-	-	-	-		

Source: All statistical data is gathered from the official Compulsory School Statistics (GSI).

Source: GSI.
This data covers all pupils recognised as having SEN – those with and without a decision. In the public sector there are 50,263 pupils with a decision and 300 without. In the private sector there are 1,590 pupils with a decision and 26 without.

Source: GSI.
The number of pupils with SEN in segregated settings is according to the GSI-data.

Source: GSI.
* GSI does not have data for the primary secondary breakdown for this question.
** This is a change from the data provided in the 2010 exercise when pupils in mainstream classes receiving extra tutoring for specific subjects – such as Norwegian or mathematics – were included. Pupils receiving such support are not included in this data.

Source: GSI.
* GSI does not have data for the primary secondary breakdown for this question.

6. Compulsory age phase	Age 6–15 (10 years of schooling). Primary school age 6–12, secondary school age 13–15.
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>Private schools are regarded primarily as a supplement to local authority schools. Most private schools are run by religious denominations or by organisations representing specific views of life or alternative educational approaches. Some offer essential instruction that the local authority schools are unable to provide. Authorised private schools receive financial support from the State.</p> <p>Legal definition:</p> <p>Government dependent private schools Section 2–1 (Private school act) Primary and secondary schools and high schools. The Ministry must approve all private schools. Approval can be granted when a school fulfils the requirements laid down in the private school act, i.e. curriculum, assessment, the organisation of the pupils' learning environment and budget.</p> <p>Independent private schools Section 2–12 (Education Act) Private primary and lower secondary schools. The Ministry must approve private primary and lower secondary schools. Approval shall be granted when a school fulfils the requirements laid down in the Act relating to Primary and Secondary Education, especially when it comes to curriculum, assessment and the organisation of the pupils' learning environment. In the case of foreign and international primary and lower secondary schools in Norway, the Ministry may grant exemptions from the requirements.</p> <p>Persons who run private primary and lower secondary schools without such approval are liable to fines.</p>
8. Legal definition of SEN	<p>Right to special education:</p> <p>Pupils who either do not or are unable to benefit satisfactorily from mainstream tuition have the right to special education. In assessing what kind of tuition shall be provided, particular emphasis shall be placed on the pupil's developmental prospects. The content of the courses offered shall be such that the pupil receives adequate benefit from the tuition as a whole in relation to other pupils and in relation to educational objectives that are realistic for the pupil. Pupils who receive special needs education shall have the same total number of teaching hours as other pupils.</p> <p>Expert assessment: Before the municipality or the county authority makes a decision concerning special education or a decision concerning special educational assistance, an expert assessment shall be made of the pupil's specific needs. This assessment shall determine whether the pupil needs special education, and what kind of tuition should be provided. The expert assessment shall consider and determine the following – the pupil's benefit from mainstream tuition, learning difficulties the pupil has and other special conditions of importance to tuition, realistic educational objectives for the pupil, whether it is possible to provide help for the pupil's difficulties within mainstream educational provision and what kind of tuition it is appropriate to provide.</p> <p>The Ministry may issue further regulations concerning expert assessment. If the decision of the municipality or county authority differs from the expert assessment, it shall be explained in the grounds for the decision why the municipality or county authority is of the opinion that the tuition received by the pupil fulfils the pupil's rights.</p>

POLAND

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	5,151,923		156,412			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	5,308,335	2010/2011
	2,516,652	2,635,271	72,092	84,320		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	154,870		5,976			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	160,846 *	2010/2011
	68,818	86,052	1,900	4,076		
<p>Source: Ministry of National Education (SIO: System of Educational Information). * Data is collected in all compulsory schools about pupils who have an official decision about the need for special education or about the need for rehabilitation and educational activities (individual/group). There is no separate data available about the number of pupils with other SENs. Data is collected on the number of pupils who receive support (psychological and pedagogical) in educational settings. The data includes students who attend all types of school and rehabilitation and education centres. This applies to questions 2 to 5.</p>						
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	86,587		4,496			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	91,083	2010/2011
	30,206	56,381	1,058	3,438		
<p>Source: Ministry of National Education (SIO: System of Educational Information). The data includes students who attend to special schools and rehabilitation and educational centres.</p>						
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	2,501		87			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	2,588	2010/2011
	987	1,514	45	42		
<p>Source: Ministry of National Education (SIO: System of Educational Information).</p>						

5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Ministry of National Education (SIO: System of Educational Information). * The data includes pupils who need special education and attend integration or mainstream classes.
	65,782		1,393				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	37,625	28,157	797	596			
6. Compulsory age phase	<p>Primary – from 7 up to 13 (students who require a special education – with disability, socially maladjusted or at risk of social maladjustment, can study in primary school longer – up to 18). Data include 6-year-old children who fulfil the pre-school one-year compulsory education. The pre-school one-year education could be pursued in the kindergartens, kindergarten classes in the primary schools or in the different forms of the pre-school education.</p> <p>Secondary (lower and upper) – lower secondary school (gymnasium) from 13 up to 16 (students who require a special education – with disability, socially maladjusted or at risk of social maladjustment, can study in this type of school up to 21). Upper secondary school (general, vocational) from 16–18, 19 or 20 (depends on the type of school). The students who require a special education – with disability, socially maladjusted or at risk of social maladjustment, can study in the upper secondary school up to 24).</p> <p>For students with disability, socially maladjusted and at risk of social maladjustment the compulsory education must be finished no later than when they are 24 years old. Students with a deep mental retardation could attend the rehabilitation and educational activities until they are 25 years old.</p>						
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>In line with the Education Act of 1991, schools can be public and non-public. A public school is an educational institution established by the central administration, local/district/regional authorities and other legal body or by an individual person. It provides free education and implements core curricula and assessment procedures established by the relevant Minister of National Education.</p> <p>A non-public school is an educational institution run by the legal bodies or individual persons on the basis of their incorporation into the register of non-public schools.</p> <p>Non-public schools are financed within the framework of a general subsidy from the state budget and additionally by fees received from parents and funds.</p> <p>Non-public schools in Poland have the right to issue school certificates that are recognised by all other schools and by universities.</p>						
8. Legal definition of SEN	<p>In Poland the legal changes in the organisation of education of pupils with special educational needs were made in 2010. The changes were systemic in nature and aimed to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - more flexible model of education which fits individual pupil needs - create conditions for systematic increasing the quality of teaching methods - prepare pupils to make aware, vocational decisions - provide better access to the early support in the development and education inc. early intervention and pre-school education - provide forms and conditions of the external exams adopted to the nature of the disability. <p>The concept of special educational needs is understood very broadly. Children or young people have special educational needs if their opportunities for education, development and learning are limited to such an extent that they cannot meet the educational requirements at mainstream schools without receiving additional assistance, both throughout the entire educational process (for example: because of disability, specific learning difficulties) or during certain period of education (a child showing signs of emotional problems resulting from trauma). In the group of children with special educational needs are pupils with long-term illness, adaptive problems, specific learning difficulties (dyslexia, dysgraphia,</p>						

dyscalculia), speech impairments, trauma-induced emotional and behavioural difficulties, any other learning difficulties and gifted children as well. Among the pupils with special educational needs are distinguished children who require special organisation of education and teaching methods. This means that such children need broad specialist support during their education, with adapted curriculum and adjusted learning conditions. These children get the decision from a public counselling centre for youth and children about the need of the special education. The children with a deep mental retardation fulfil the compulsory education by attending the rehabilitation and educational activities (in individual or group form) on the basis of the decision of a public counselling centre for youth and children.

Within the group who require the special education are distinguished disabled children (physically disabled, intellectually disabled, blind, visually impaired, deaf, hearing impaired, autistic, with multiple impairments) and pupils with abnormal social functioning (socially maladjusted youth who need reclamation and young people at risk of social maladjustment who need socio-therapy).

Ministry of National Education collects data about the number of children who have the decision about a need of special education or a need of the rehabilitation and education activities due to the deep mental retardation. There are collected data about the whole number of pupils who get a support (psychological and pedagogical) in the educational settings in every school year but not about number of children who have special educational needs and do not need the special education.

Special needs education is regulated by the Act on School Education of 7 September 1991, with further amendments and the implementing regulations of Minister of National Education about special needs education.

Children with SEN could attend to every type of school. All students with SEN receive assistance from a kindergarten or a school they attended and from a public counselling centres for youth and children free of charge and on a voluntary basis. Results of psychological, pedagogical and medical assessment serve as a basis for qualifying pupils for suitable forms of education (mainstream schools, integration schools, special schools, residential special schools, rehabilitation and education centres) although the final decision belongs to the parents.

PORTUGAL

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (<i>including those with SEN</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	1,153,193		196,518			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	1,349,711	2009/2010
	608,753	544,440	82,175	114,343		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (<i>in all educational settings</i>)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	41,181		1,975			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	43,156	2011/2012
	26,409	14,772	1,975	-		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	- *		1,975			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	1,975	2011/2012
	-	-	1,975	-		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	1,055		- *			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	1,055	2011/2012
	890	165	-	-		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	40,126		- *			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	40,126	2009/2010
	25,519	14,607	-	-		

6. Compulsory age phase	Compulsory education covers from 6 to 18 years of age. Primary phase age ranges from 6 to 12 years of age. Secondary phase age ranges from 13 to 18 years of age.
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	The private special education schools are funded by the state according to the laws nº 1102/97 and nº 1103/97, 3 November.
8. Legal definition of SEN	Children and young people receiving special education because they have difficulties in their learning process and their participation considering the interaction between inter-related factors and limitations in their functioning (law nº 3/2008, 7 January).

SLOVAKIA

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils <i>(including those with SEN)</i>	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	440,862		30,144			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	471,006	2011/2012
	195,042	245,820	13,072	17,072		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN <i>(in all educational settings)</i>	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	46,413		2,566			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	48,979	2011/2012
	17,052	29,361	906	1,660		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	17,028		967			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	17,995	2011/2012
	6,633	10,395	466	501		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	10,202		173			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	10,375	2011/2012
	4,174	6,028	25	148		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	19,183		14,26			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	20,609	2011/2012
	6,245	12,938	415	1,011		

6. Compulsory age phase	6–16 years.
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	Public sector: kindergartens are maintained by local government. Schools are maintained by local and county government. Private sector: schools and kindergartens are maintained by the church, foundation or private person. Public and private schools are financed by the state; private schools can collect contribution from parents. Both of them use curriculum of state.
8. Legal definition of SEN	A child in kindergarten and pupil in school is child/pupil with SEN, when he/she has SEN identified by special team in advisory service – special pedagogue, psychologist and physician. Categories of children and pupils with SEN by reason of: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- health handicap: physical, mental, sensory, speech and language impairment, autism and children with severe multiple needs;- health risk conditions;- specific learning difficulties;- behavioural difficulties;- social disadvantage;- (extreme) intellectual talent.

SLOVENIA

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	162,902		- *			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	162,544	2011/2012
	162,544	-	-	-		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	12,000		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	12,000	2011/2012
	12,000	-	-	-		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	2,922		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	2,922 *	2011/2012
	2,922	-	-	-		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	437		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	437	2011/2012
	437	-	-	-		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	8,641		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	8,641	2011/2012
	8,641	-	-	-		

6. Compulsory age phase	In Slovenia only primary school is compulsory; pupils aged 6 enter the 9-year compulsory school.
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	Private schools are not a part of the public educational system. Their status makes them distinct from those schools which operate on the basis of concession agreement and their programmes do not differ from programmes of public schools. The expression 'private schools' also includes private schools which carry out their educational programmes according to the internationally valid pedagogical principles (Steiner, Decroly, Montessori, etc.).
8. Legal definition of SEN	In legalisation we have the following groups of disabled children (pupils): <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Children with mental disabilities;- Blind and visually impaired children;- Children with hearing impairments and deafness;- Children with speech and language problems;- Physically disabled children;- Children with long-term illnesses;- Children with learning difficulties; and- Children with emotional and behaviour problems.

SPAIN

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	2,998,517		1,496,671			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	4,495,188	2009/2010
	1,818,290	1,180,227	884,109	612,562		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	78,191		28,786			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	106,977	2009/2010
	48,075	30,116	14,679	14,107		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	8,356		6,554			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	14,910 *	2009/2010
	4,324	4,032	2,983	3,571		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	1,563		1,226			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	2,789 *	2009/2012
	809	754	558	668		
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	68,272		21,006			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	89,278	2009/2010
	42,942	25,330	11,138	9,868		
6. Compulsory age phase	6–15 years. Compulsory primary education: from 6 to 12 years.					

	Compulsory secondary education: from 12 to 15 years.
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>Public education: the educational settings belong to a public authority. All the funding – including teachers’ salary (teachers are civil servants) – is provided by the public authority, totally free of charge. The majority of Spanish pupils/students are schooled in this sector.</p> <p>Private education: private educational establishments are owned by private natural or legal persons. These private establishments may reach agreements with the Administration, in which case they are known as subsidised private schools. Parents pay for the schooling.</p>
8. Legal definition of SEN	<p>Students with special educational needs refer to those who require certain support and specific educational attention due to disability or serious behavioural disorder, either for a period or throughout the whole of their schooling.</p> <p>It is the responsibility of the Education Administrations to guarantee and regulate the schooling of these children and ensure the participation of parents or guardians in the decisions which affect the schooling and educational procedures of these students. It is also their responsibility to adopt the appropriate measures to provide parents of these children with adequate individual assessment and the necessary information to help them in the education of their children.</p> <p>The schooling of students with special educational need will be governed by principles of normalisation and inclusion and will ensure non-discrimination and real equality in the access to the education system and continued attendance, allowing flexibility in the different stages of their education when necessary. The schooling of these students in special education centres or units, which may be extended until the age of twenty-one, will only take place when their needs cannot be met by the special needs provisions available in mainstream schools.</p> <p>The identification and assessment of the educational needs of these students will be carried out as early as possible by qualified professionals under the conditions determined by the Education Administrations.</p> <p>At the end of each school year the results obtained from each student will be assessed, according to the objectives set out in the initial assessment. This will allow the staff to provide appropriate guidance and adapt the learning programme in order to encourage, as far as possible, better integration of these students.</p> <p>It is the responsibility of the Education Administrations to provide infant school provision for children with special educational needs and to develop appropriate schooling programmes for them in primary and secondary schools.</p> <p>It is also the responsibility of the Education Administrations to encourage students with special educational needs to continue with the post-compulsory education as appropriate and to modify as necessary the testing procedures established in this Law for those students with disabilities.</p> <p>Pupils with special educational needs can attend both special education and mainstream establishments. Schooling should preferably be provided in mainstream establishments, adapting such programmes to each pupil’s capacities.</p> <p>Reference: LOE: Título II, Capítulo I, Sección primera: Alumnado que presenta necesidades educativas especiales.</p>

SWEDEN

Question	Data				Notes and sources used	
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	781,351		105,136			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	886,487	2010/2011
	-	-	-	-		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	12,117		499			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	12,616 *	2010/2011
	-	-	-	-		
<p>Source: Database of the Swedish National Agency for Education.</p> <p>* A breakdown of pupils in primary and secondary phases in both the public and private sectors is not available. This applies to questions 1 to 5. However, the breakdown of pupils across both sectors in primary and secondary education is as follows: Primary: 299,954; Secondary: 586,533.</p>						
<p>Source: Database of the Swedish National Agency for Education.</p> <p>It should be noted that there are no overall statistics available for Sweden. In 2007 the Swedish National Agency for Education investigated the possibility of producing national statistics on pupils with disabilities. The National Agency found that such statistics would not be reliable, mainly because of the difficulty in defining what is to be counted as disability and how statistically to group the pupils and that it would shift focus from the responsibility of the school to support all pupils to the problems of the individual.</p> <p>* These pupils have cognitive disabilities who are enrolled in the special programmes and pupils who attend a national special school for: pupils with visual impairment and additional disabilities; severe speech and language disorder; deafness or impaired hearing combined severe learning disabilities or congenital deaf-blindness. A breakdown of pupils in primary and secondary phases in each of the public and private sectors is as follows: Primary: 2,674; Secondary: 9,441. This figure includes 887 pupils above compulsory school age. These pupils are entitled to a</p>						

							voluntary tenth school year to broaden or deepen their knowledge.
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Swedish National Agency for Education. * These pupils attend a national special school for pupils with: visual impairment and additional disabilities, severe speech and language disorder; deafness or impaired hearing combined severe learning disabilities; congenital deaf-blindness. This figure includes 64 pupils above compulsory school age. These pupils are entitled to a voluntary tenth school year to broaden or deepen their knowledge.
	501 *		0				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	111	390	0	0	501	2010/2011	
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools *	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Swedish National Agency for Education. * These figures cover pupils with cognitive disabilities who are enrolled in the special programmes. These programmes are offered in every municipality and pupils are more or less included in the mainstream school. The breakdown of pupils across both sectors in primary and secondary education is as follows: Primary: 2,674; Secondary: 9,441. This figure includes 887 pupils above compulsory school age. These pupils are entitled to a voluntary tenth school year to broaden or deepen their knowledge.
	11,616		499				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	12,115 *	2010/2011	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	* In Sweden, there are an unknown number of pupils with SEN who are fully included in mainstream classes. Data is not collected relating to these pupils.
	-		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	- *	-	
6. Compulsory age phase	The compulsory age phase is 7 to 16 years. Primary age phase is 7 to 9 years. Secondary age phase is 10 to 16 years.						
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	A majority of Swedish schools are public, run by municipalities, but an increasing number are independent. Independent schools on the compulsory level need to be certified by the National Agency for Education and they are financed by municipality subsidies. The municipality where the student lives pays the school a 'per student, per year grant'. Independent schools are open to everyone and free of charge.						

8. Legal definition of SEN

Please refer to notes above for a clear indication of which pupils the data refers to. There is no legal definition of SEN. In Sweden education follows the principle of 'a school for all' and the focus is on what kind of support the student needs – access to equivalent education for all. This means that pupils in need of special support should not be treated or defined as a group that is any different from other pupils and their rights are not stated separately. The obligation for schools to attend to all pupils' needs is, however, emphasised.

Pupils in need of special support have the right to specialist provision. Special support shall be given to pupils who have difficulties in completing their education successfully. If a pupil needs special support an Action Plan shall be drawn up. The regulations regarding plans for pupils in need of special support have been further clarified. The pupil's need is to be assessed and the subsequent Action Plan shall contain information regarding the pupil's needs, what measures will be taken and how these measures will be followed up and evaluated. All education corresponds as far as possible to the National curricula, but with the emphasis upon meeting individual learning needs. In a few circumstances, this provision is offered in special settings, e.g. Special Schools with sign language communication are available for pupils with severe hearing impairments.

Reference: All information is taken from Swedish school law and National curriculum documents, e.g. Education Act (1985:1100) Ch.1. General Provisions, Curriculum for the Pre-school Lpfo 98, Curriculum for the Compulsory School System, the Pre-School Class and the Leisure-time Centre Lpo 94, Curriculum for the Non-Compulsory School System Lpf 94.

SWITZERLAND

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	713,325		44,010			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary		
	432,673)	280,652	22,180	21,830	757,335	2010/2011
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	24,737		12,598			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary		
	15,781	8,956	7,074	5,524	37,335	2010/2011
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	-		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary		
	-	-	-	-	- *	-
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	-		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary		
	-	-	-	-	- *	-
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	-		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary		
	-	-	-	-	- *	-

6. Compulsory age phase	<p>Compulsory: 4–16 years.</p> <p>Pre-primary education: from 4 to 6 years old (ISCED 0).</p> <p>Primary education: from 6 to 12 years old (ISCED 1).</p> <p>Lower secondary education: from 12 to 16 years old (ISCED 2).</p>
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>The public schools are fully funded by the government.</p> <p>The private sector includes schools with or without public subsidies.</p>
8. Legal definition of SEN	<p>Inter-cantonal agreement of collaboration in the domain of Special Needs Education:</p> <p>Individuals entitled to benefits:</p> <p>Children and youth from birth on to 20 years of age, living in Switzerland, have the right to adequate provision of special educational services, providing that the following conditions are met:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prior to compulsory education: if it can be established that the development of the child is limited or at risk or that following instruction in a mainstream classrooms without specific support will not be possible for the child; - During compulsory education: if it can be established that possibilities of development and education are limited in such a manner that instruction in mainstream classrooms cannot be followed without specific support any more or if other special educational needs are established. <p>Art 3. Inter-cantonal Agreement of Collaboration in the Domain of Special Needs Education, 25 October 2007. (Interkantonale Vereinbarung über die Zusammenarbeit im Bereich der Sonderpädagogik vom 25.Oktober 2007).</p>

UNITED KINGDOM (ENGLAND)

Question	Data				Notes and sources used	
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils <i>(including those with SEN)</i>	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	7,504,300		580,650			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	8,084,950 *	2010/2011
	-	-	-	-		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN <i>(in all educational settings)</i>	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	212,990		13,220			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	226,210 *	2010/2011
	-	-	-	-		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	86,110		13,220			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	99,330 *	2010/2011
	-	-	-	-		

Source: Department for Education (DFE). SFR 14/2011 – Special Educational Needs in England, January 2011 (Table 1A).
 * For all data, it is not possible to give an exact primary/secondary school split. This applies to questions 1 to 5.
 The data includes pupils of all ages of sole and dual main registration and has been rounded up to the nearest 10.

Source: Department for Education (DFE). SFR 14/2011 – Special Educational Needs in England, January 2011 (Table 2).
 * All data covers pupils with statements (official recognition of SEN) only. This applies to all data presented in questions 2 to 5.

Source: Department for Education (DFE). SFR 14/2011 – Special Educational Needs in England, January 2011 (Table 2).
 * This figure is for all pupils in some form of special school. This includes:
 - in the public sector maintained special schools (including foundation schools): 86,110
 - in the private sector non-maintained special schools 3,380
 - independent special schools: 7,660
 - other independent schools: 2,180.

4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Department for Education (DFE). SFR 14/2011 – Special Educational Needs in England, January 2011 (Table 2). * Data for the private sector is not available. ** This figure is for all pupils in some form of segregated class in a mainstream school: resourced provision/special classes in maintained mainstream schools; SEN units in maintained mainstream schools.
	15,490		- *				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	15,490 **	2010/2011	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Department for Education (DFE). SFR 14/2011 – Special Educational Needs in England, January 2011 (Table 2). * Data for the private sector is not available. ** This figure is for all pupils in fully inclusive settings in: maintained mainstream schools (including foundation schools); pupil referral units; hospital schools; academies; pupils who are excluded and where other arrangements are made for them: There are 2,040 pupils who are either awaiting placement or their parents have made alternative arrangements for them. It is not possible to indicate where they are educated and they are not included in these figures.
	111,390		- *				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	111,390 **	2010/2011	
6. Compulsory age phase	Compulsory school age is from 5–16.						
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	<p>Private schools are schools which are largely funded through fees paid by parents. There is private provision at all levels of education. Private schools are known as independent schools (or, confusingly, 'public schools') and they do not receive direct government funding, although some independent schools have charitable status and benefit from tax relief and they may also apply for some public support, for example, the National Lottery funding scheme. Some independent schools are wholly or mainly for children with SEN and local authorities can place children in independent schools, either independent special or mainstream schools.</p> <p>In England, Academies are independent schools in law but are state-funded rather than funded through fees. Academies are the equivalent of local authority maintained schools but are not under local authorities and have greater freedom in deciding things like teachers pay. Local authority maintained mainstream or special schools are publicly funded and they must follow the National Curriculum which other schools are not obliged to do.</p> <p>Non-maintained special schools (NMSS) are schools in England approved by the Secretary of State for Education as special schools that are not maintained by the state, but charge fees on a non-profit making basis. Most NMSS are run by major charities or charitable trusts. Most</p>						

	places in NMSS are purchased by local authorities for pupils for whom there is no there is no available appropriate provision in a local authority maintained school: parents rarely pay fees directly to these schools.
8. Legal definition of SEN	<p>The legal definition of special educational needs is set out in the Education Act 1996, section 312:</p> <p>(1) A child has 'special educational needs' for the purposes of this Act if (s)he has a learning difficulty which calls for special educational provision to be made for him.</p> <p>(2) Subject to subsection (3) ... a child has a 'learning difficulty' for the purposes of this Act if:</p> <p>(a) she/he has a significantly greater difficulty in learning than the majority of children of her/his age,</p> <p>(b) she/he has a disability which either prevents or hinders her/him from making use of educational facilities of a kind generally provided for children of her/his age in schools within the area of the local education authority, or</p> <p>(c) she/he is under compulsory school age and is, or would be if special educational provision were not made for her/him, likely to fall within paragraph (a) or (b) when of ... that age.</p> <p>(3) A child is not to be taken as having a learning difficulty solely because the language (or form of the language) in which he is, or will be, taught is different from a language (or form of a language) which has at any time been spoken in her/his home.</p> <p>(4) In this Act 'special educational provision' means:</p> <p>(a) in relation to a child who has attained the age of two, educational provision which is additional to, or otherwise different from, the educational provision made generally for children of her/his age in schools maintained by the local education authority (other than special schools) ... , and</p> <p>(b) in relation to a child under that age, educational provision of any kind.</p> <p>(5) In this Part:</p> <p>'child' includes any person who has not attained the age of 19 and is a registered pupil at a school;</p> <p>'maintained school' means any community, foundation or voluntary school or any community or foundation special school not established in a hospital.</p>

UNITED KINGDOM (NORTHERN IRELAND)

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	276,399 *		- **			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	276,399	2011/2012
	157,373	119,026	-	-		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	12,891 *		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	12,891	2011/2012
	6,077	6,814	-	-		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	3,595 *		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	3,595	2011/2012
	1,679	1,916	-	-		
4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	1,646 *		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	1,646	2011/2012
	907	739	-	-		

Source: Northern Ireland School Census 2011/2012.
 * For the purpose of this exercise primary includes years 1–7 only and post primary includes years 8–12.
 ** Census data does not include information on independent/private sector schools. Such schools operate outside the SEN Framework. No data is available for pupils in the private sector for questions 1 to 5.

Source: Northern Ireland School Census 2011/2012.
 * SEN is categorised as level 1–5. Only pupils with statements (SEN level 5) are included in the analysis.

Source: Northern Ireland School Census 2011/2012. Special schools.
 * Pupils assigned to primary or post primary dependent on age.

Source: Northern Ireland School Census 2011/2012.
 * Pupils attend special units in mainstream schools.

5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Northern Ireland School Census 2011/2012.
	7,650		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	3,491	4,159	-	-	7,650	2011/2012	
6. Compulsory age phase	4 years of age to 16 years of age as defined in Article 46 of the Education and Libraries (Northern Ireland) (Order 1986).						
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	Census data does not include information on independent/private sector schools. Such schools operate outside the SEN Framework.						
8. Legal definition of SEN	Article 3 of the Education (Northern Ireland) Order 1996 defines a child as having special educational needs if he or she has a learning difficulty that calls for special educational provision to be made for him or her.						

UNITED KINGDOM (SCOTLAND)

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils <i>(including those with SEN)</i>	Public Sector		Private Sector *		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	585,289		30,507			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	615,796	Public sector: 2011/2012 Private sector: 2009/2010 *
	369,093	216,196	11,527	18,980		
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN <i>(in all educational settings)</i>	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	87,832		4,199			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	92,031	Public sector: 2011/2012 Private sector: 2009/2010
	53,650	34,182	1,187	3,012		
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	5,595		982			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary	6,577	Public sector: 2011/2012 Private sector: 2009/2010
	2,674	2,921	88	894		

4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Adhoc analysis of the Scottish Government Pupils in Scotland 2011 data.
	3,106		0				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	2,123	983	0	0	3,106	Public sector: 2011/2012 Private sector: 2009/2010	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Source: Adhoc analysis of the Scottish Government Pupils in Scotland 2011 data. * This includes all pupils with additional support needs (ASN) in mainstream schools who spend less than 20% of their time in segregated special classes.
	79,131		3,217				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	48,853	30,278	1,099	2,118	82,348 *	Public sector: 2011/2012 Private sector: 2009/2010	
6. Compulsory age phase	<p>The usual arrangements for pupils entering the first class of primary school are that children whose 5th birthday falls between the start of March and the end of February start school together in the August in the middle of that period. However, parents may choose to defer entry.</p> <p>Pupils who reach the age of 16 between 1 March and 30 September of a given year can leave that summer, or if they reach 16 from 1 October to the following end of February can leave at the end of winter term during that period.</p> <p>Public sector: primary phase pupils are pupils aged 4 or older in primary schools or pupils aged 4 to 11 years in special schools. Secondary phase pupils are pupils in secondary schools aged under 16 or pupils aged 12 to 15 years in special schools.</p> <p>Private sector: primary phase pupils above are in primary schools or are pupils under 12 in special schools. Secondary phase pupils are pupils in secondary schools or pupils aged 12 or over in special schools.</p>						
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	Publicly funded schools are local authority and grant-aided schools. A grant-aided school is a school in receipt of funding from the Scottish Government.						

8. Legal definition of SEN	<p>Definition of Additional Support Needs (ASN) in The Education (Additional Support for Learning) (Scotland) Act 2004 (as amended):</p> <p>(1) A child or young person has additional support needs for the purposes of this Act where, for whatever reason, the child or young person is, or is likely to be, unable without the provision of additional support to benefit from school education provided or to be provided for the child or young person.</p> <p>(1A) Without prejudice to the generality of subsection (1), a child or young person has additional support needs if the child or young person is looked after by a local authority (within the meaning of section 17(6) of the Children (Scotland) Act 1995 (c.36)).</p> <p>(1B) But where, in the course of identifying (in accordance with the arrangements made by them under section 6(1)(b)) the particular additional support needs of a child or young person who is looked after by a local authority (within the meaning of section 17(6) of the Children (Scotland) Act 1995 (c.36)), an education authority form the view that the child or young person is, or is likely to be, able without the provision of additional support to benefit from school education provided to or to be provided for the child or young person, subsection (1A) ceases to apply.</p> <p>1(3) In this Act, 'additional support' means -</p> <p>(a) in relation to a prescribed pre-school child, a child of school age or a young person receiving school education, provision (whether or not educational provision) which is additional to, or otherwise different from, the educational provision made generally for children or, as the case may be, young persons of the same age in schools (other than special schools) under the management of the education authority responsible for the school education of the child or young person, or in the case where there is no such authority, the education authority for the area to which the child or young person belongs,</p> <p>(b) in relation to a child under school age other than a prescribed pre-school child, such provision (whether or not educational provision) as is appropriate in the circumstances.</p>
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UNITED KINGDOM (WALES)

Question	Data					Notes and sources used
1. Number of compulsory school aged pupils (including those with SEN)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	363,765		6,392			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary		
	193,374	170,391	2,357	4,035	370,157	2011/2012
2. Number of compulsory school aged pupils who have SEN (in all educational settings)	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	11,125 *		221 **			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary		
	4,408	6,717	21	200	11,346 ***	2011/2012
3. Pupils with SEN in segregated special schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference
	3,005		-			
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary		
	998	2007	-	-	3,005 *	2011/2012

4. Pupils with SEN in segregated special classes in mainstream schools	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	Although there are special classes in maintained schools it is not possible to breakdown the information to show either the compulsory school age group or whether or not the pupil has a statement of SEN, as required here. This is a change from the 2010 dataset.
	-		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	-	2011/2012	
5. Pupils with SEN in fully inclusive settings	Public Sector		Private Sector		Total	Academic Year of Reference	See note for question 4. This is a change from the 2010 dataset.
	-		-				
	Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary			
	-	-	-	-	-	2011/2012	
6. Compulsory age phase	Compulsory school age is classed as pupils aged 5–15 years of age.						
7. Clarification of Public - Private sector education	Public sector education – education which is controlled by the Government. Private sector education – independent fee-paying schools.						
8. Legal definition of SEN	<p>Children have special educational needs if they have a learning difficulty which calls for special educational provision to be made for them.</p> <p>Children have a learning difficulty if they:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Have a significantly greater difficulty in learning than the majority of children of the same age; or b) Have a disability which prevents or hinders them from making use of educational facility of a kind generally provided for children of the same age in schools within the area of the local education authority; c) Are under compulsory school age and fall within the definition at (a) or (b) above or would do so if special educational provision was not made for them. <p>Special educational provision means:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) For children of two or over, educational provision which is additional to, or otherwise different from, the educational provision made generally available for children of their age in schools maintained by the LA, other than special schools, in the area; b) For children under two, educational provision of any kind. <p>SEN Code of Practice for Wales 2002.</p>						

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